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Research article

Regional self-sufficiency: A multi-dimensional analysis relating agricultural production and consumption in the European Union

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ABSTRACT

Short food supply chains and circularity are discussed as key factors for a sustainable food system. Although self-sufficiency ratios (SSR) are often used to characterize agri-food systems, the concept of SSR remains inconsistently defined, particularly when means of production such as livestock feed are explicitly considered. We present a systematic conceptualization of SSR, i.e., the ratio of domestic production to consumption within a region along three dimensions: a) livestock products, b) cropland products, and c) primary agricultural biomass. While a) and b) refer to the domestic production and net-trade of livestock resp. crop products, c) relates to domestic agricultural primary production and primary biomass consumption representing the feed embodied in consumed livestock products. As such, the third dimension indicates the potential self-sufficiency for a region assuming consumed livestock products stem from domestic livestock, fed with domestic crops and grass. We quantify these three SSR dimensions for 226 regions (NUTS2) in the European Union (EU) based on detailed agricultural statistics and models. Results show that 14 % of EU regions were self-sufficient, and 26 % were import-dependent for all three dimensions. We find that 54 % of regions were self-sufficient for ruminant livestock products and 39 % for monogastric livestock products underlining a spatially concentrated pork, egg, and poultry production structure in the EU. Moreover, 21 % of regions are dependent on crop imports and simultaneously self-sufficient or net-exporters of livestock products. Our investigation on the relationship between agricultural production and consumption discloses a widespread disconnectedness of European livestock systems between land use and consumption. Expanding a narrow understanding of food self-sufficiency by integrating a primary biomass perspective allows for a more nuanced debate on sustainable agri-food systems. The results, first, demonstrate the substantial role of net-trade in the supply of regional food systems and, second, indicate room for stronger circular integration of crop- and livestock systems.

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1. Introduction

Agri-food systems belong to the most critical interactions between the human and natural sphere due to their indispensable role in supplying food and securing livelihoods (Oteros-Rozas et al., 2019). Humanity faces the challenge of transforming agri-food systems to secure accessible and healthy diets produced in accordance with planetary boundaries (Clark et al., 2020; Rockström et al., 2020). Technological solutions, agroecological farming practices, and plant-based diets are only a few among discussed innovative options to address the biodiversity and climate crisis (Bezner Kerr et al., 2021; Gerssen-Gondelach

et al., 2017; Kalt et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2022). Specifically, short food supply chains realized in local or regional food systems have gained popularity as a vision for a sustainable agri-food system (Bisoffi et al., 2021; Sonnino, 2013).

Regional food systems are associated with numerous valuable attributes such as closed nutrient flows, close relationships between consumer and producer, healthy diets due to the availability of fresh and nutritious food, and a small carbon footprint caused by short transport distance (Billen et al., 2021; Pradhan et al., 2020; Sonnino, 2013). Yet, estimates suggest that only one-third of the global population can be supplied locally (Kinnunen et al., 2020; Kriewald et al., 2019), indicating that food supplies from other regions, countries, and even continents are crucial for global food security (Kummu et al., 2020). Today, the global agri-food system is characterized by a complex web of trade flows, which establishes widespread connectivity between distant places with causes and effects on various spatial and societal scales (denoted as teleconnections) (Dorninger et al., 2021; Kastner et al., 2014;

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Tramberend et al., 2019). As one very recent and impactful example, the 2022 Russian invasion of Ukraine reduced exports from two of the most important agricultural producers and put additional 8 to 13 million people, mainly in Asia-Pacific and Sub-Saharan Africa, at risk for undernourishment (FAO, 2022). Shortly before, closed borders due to the COVID-19-pandemic challenged global trade chains and fueled the discussion on the resilience of disconnected agri-food systems and regional self-sufficiency (Helleiner, 2021; Hobbs, 2020; Roubik et al., 2022).

Self-sufficiency, expressed as the ratio between domestic agricultural production and consumption, indicates a region's reliance on net-imports. National food self-sufficiency became a key indicator for food availability, a fundamental pillar of food security, despite arguments by mainstream economists that a focus on self-sufficiency can threaten food security as it neglects efficiency advantages resulting from international trade (Clapp, 2017; Naylor and Falcon, 2010). Notwithstanding, self-sufficiency, although often undefined, constitutes a major aim of agri-food policies (Clapp, 2017). Today, self-sufficiency ratios (SSR) are standard indicators in agricultural and economic statistics measured in energy, proteins, physical or monetary volumes (Beltran-Peña et al., 2020; Godenau et al., 2020; O'Hagan, 1976).

Agricultural production and consumption characteristics and, notably, the livestock system in the European Union are highly diverse between and within nations (Du et al., 2021; Leip et al., 2015). Extreme examples are urban areas with their specific combination of a small agricultural sector and significant food demand due to high population densities. Teleconnections of urban food systems usually extend far beyond the surrounding areas, which has stimulated research on metropolitan foodsheds, urban land teleconnections (Barthel et al., 2019; Seto et al., 2012), and the ability of local supply and the degree of self-sufficiency (Schreiber et al., 2021; Zasada et al., 2019). Next to urban case studies, a general shift to more spatially disaggregated research can be observed. For example, Lin et al. (2019) developed a model integrating machine learning, statistics, and linear programming to quantify food flows between 3142 counties of the United States. Croft et al. (2018) show the different contributions of Brazilian states to soy imports to the EU, and Vanham et al. (2018) analyze water footprints of sub-national regions in the United Kingdom, France, and Germany. It is argued that more detailed solutions can result in more targeted and effective policy interventions. Yet, when it comes to self-sufficiency, the focus remains on urban areas and the supplying role of rural areas. Consequently, the self-sufficiency of regions with landscapes with unfavorable conditions for agriculture or specialized land-use systems is less well researched. Consistent and systematic analyses of self-sufficiencies and the quantification of import dependencies on a sub-national scale are scarce (Du et al., 2021), which neglects differences in their potential for change, innovation, and adaptation (Doernberg and Weith, 2021).

Livestock plays a pivotal role in agricultural supply chains and international trade. Globally, approximately 60 % of total harvested biomass is used as feed, and 21 % of all feed crops consumed by livestock is traded internationally (Roux et al., 2022). Although the availability of feed requirements is a prerequisite of livestock production, it is not reflected in the SSR of livestock products (O'Hagan, 1976). Hence, while SSR seek to inform about domestic food production and food security, potential import dependencies are obscured. For example, European livestock systems are strongly dependent on protein feed imports from North and South America and simultaneously net-export livestock products (Kastner et al., 2011; Sporchia et al., 2021). Therefore, the EU's self-sufficiency ratio for pork (116 % in 2019) can only inform about food security when additionally considering the low self-sufficiency rate of 24 % for oilseed meals (European Commission, 2020, 2022). This example illustrates that focusing on the self-sufficiency of livestock products falls short of indicating import dependency when livestock's dual role as intermediate consumer and producer of agricultural products is disregarded. Yet, the assessment is not straightforward due to intricacies related to the integration of products from different processing stages as well as limited availability

for data on livestock feed, especially on the sub-national scale. Additionally, the absence of comprehensive census data on grazing - even in the EU - have resulted in high uncertainties in available assessments (Fetzel et al., 2017; Herrero et al., 2013).

In the context of sustainability studies, however, several approaches specifically account for biomass requirements of consumption patterns in order to assess the ecological impacts of resource use (Mayer et al., 2021a). In particular, footprint indicators are popular accounting methods to demonstrate the environmental effects associated with the consumption of certain products (Vanham et al., 2019). For example, the embodied Human Appropriation of Net Primary Production (eHANPP) framework explicitly addresses primary biomass as input for livestock products and indicates global land-use impacts of biomass consumption on ecosystems (Erb et al., 2009; Kastner et al., 2015). Despite challenges in the integration and appropriate mapping due to the increasing disconnectedness between feed production, livestock farming, and places of consumption (Kastner et al., 2011, 2021), it is crucial to address and uncover the so-called tele-couplings between places of production and consumption (Friis et al., 2016). Hence, we suggest that integrating livestock feed into self-sufficiency accountings would incorporate the issue of interlinked biomass flows into a widely used indicator framework and, further, allows for sustainability implications in regard to short food supply chains and the coupling of livestock and crop production in regional food systems.

This study aimed to systematically assess SSR at the NUTS2 level for the EU while consistently integrating livestock's intermediary role as an agricultural consumer (feed) and producer (animal products) at the same time. We performed calculations for 226 NUTS2-regions within the European Union (EU) and the United Kingdom (UK) in the year 2012. For this purpose, we developed a conceptual framework for the assessment of self-sufficiency in agri-food systems based on three major supply chain dimensions including livestock products, crop, and primary biomass self-sufficiency. The latter assesses the importance of import-dependency of feed required for consumed livestock products. With this analysis, we seek to provide a quantitative fundament that allows advancing the understanding of the complex interplay of agricultural production and human consumption on a sub-national scale. In doing so, it can serve as basis for forging sustainable agri-food strategies, in particular short supply chains and closed nutrient cycles and seeks to contribute to a more informed debate on regional food supply and integrated crop-livestock systems from different perspectives on agricultural biomass supply chains.

2. Methods

2.1. Conceptual framework

We here applied the concept of social metabolism, an acknowledged accounting framework for society-nature interactions to assess the sustainability of resource use. It consistently quantifies all socioeconomic inputs and outputs of material and energy of socio-economic systems following mass-balance principles (Haberl et al., 2019; Krausmann et al., 2008, 2020). Fig. 1 illustrates the social metabolism concept as applied in this study. We differentiated between agricultural biomass that is extracted from cropland and grassland for direct human consumption (e.g., cereals, vegetables) including non-food purposes, and for feeding livestock in order to produce livestock products. In accordance with standardized supply balances (e.g., published by FAOSTAT), we here simplified the diversity of supply and conversion chains and consider all products not used as livestock feed as direct human consumption. Agricultural products were either consumed domestically or exported. Accordingly, crops and livestock products were produced domestically or imported. The mass-balance principle allows estimating net-trade volumes for each region, not considering stock build-up. We assumed no inter-regional grass trade (as feed for livestock), although the exchange between regions is more likely than between nations.

Fig. 1. Representation of agricultural biomass flows applying the concept of social metabolism and material-flow accounting (Haberl et al., 2019). Variables are explained in detail in Table 1.

2.2. Self-sufficiency dimensions

Fig. 2 depicts the dimensions of self-sufficiency considered in this study, namely livestock products (S_R resp. S_M), crop (S_C), and primary biomass (S_{PC} resp. S_{PG}) self-sufficiency.

Livestock products self-sufficiency (S_R resp. S_M) compares the production of livestock products (P_R resp. P_M) with the actual human consumption in each region (C_R resp. C_M). For simplification, we summarized milk and meat from cattle and small ruminants under ‘ruminants’ (indicated by subscripted “R”) as well as meat and eggs from pigs and poultry under ‘products from monogastric animals’ (indicated by subscripted “M”). Livestock products self-sufficiency indicates net-trade of regions with products from ruminants and monogastric animals. A surplus of products ($S > 1$) denotes net-exports, and a deficit ($S < 1$) refers to the net-imports of a region.

Crop self-sufficiency (S_C) compares harvest on cropland (P_C) in a region with the consumption of crops by both human population ($C_{C, pop}$) and the domestic livestock ($C_{C, lst}$). In analogy to livestock self-sufficiency, S_C indicates a region's net-trade with crops. As a result of assuming no trade with grassland biomass, grassland harvest is equal to demand (including losses). Hence, we excluded the direct grassland ratio since all regions are self-sufficient by definition.

The livestock and crop self-sufficiency dimensions provide insights into regional crop balances and sub-national net-trade flows from a territorial perspective (also denoted as production-based accounting) (Athanasiadis et al., 2018). While this approach covers direct resource use, the consumption-based approach includes the input resources of consumed products. Both approaches have been widely applied in footprint accounting and it has been shown that particularly the combination allows to capture the full environmental performance of an entity (Athanasiadis et al., 2018; Eisenmenger et al., 2016; Erb et al., 2009; Tramberend et al., 2019).

Primary biomass self-sufficiency (S_{PC} resp. S_{PG}) compares the domestic harvest on cropland (P_C) and grassland (P_G) in a region with direct crop consumption by the local population ($C_{C, pop}$) and

feed embodied in the consumption of livestock products ($C_{C, emb}$ resp. $C_{G, emb}$). Embodied feed denotes the amount of feed crops and grass required to produce livestock products (Mayer et al., 2021a). This perspective assesses the ability to supply a hypothetical livestock herd that would meet the demand of animal-sourced products by the local population under current domestic agricultural production characteristics (e.g., harvest yields, livestock efficiency). More specifically, this dimension assumes that livestock product consumption ($C_R + C_M$) equals livestock production ($P_R + P_M$). Here, straw used for feed is included. Equally to crop self-sufficiency (S_C), crop production (P_C) and direct crop consumption for food and other uses ($C_{C, pop}$) are determining factors of primary biomass self-sufficiency (S_{BM}). Instead of current livestock feed ($C_{C, lst}$), the demand is determined by livestock feed required to produce domestically consumed animal-sourced products (=embodied feed demand). We obtained embodied feed demand by multiplying populations' demand for animal-sourced products with region-specific feed conversion ratios (FCR). In contrast to direct accounting (crop self-sufficiency), the hypothetical availability of sufficient grassland harvest needed for domestic demand is included (S_{PG}). It is the ratio between domestic grass harvest and grass required for domestically consumed animal products. The result indicates the primary biomass footprint of the domestic population.

Despite a multi-dimensional assessment of self-sufficiency, applied indices are high aggregates of a great variety of biomass products. The indices summarize products with differing water, energy, and protein contents (e.g., S_R comprises milk and meat from cattle and small ruminants; S_C merges cereals, pulses, or vegetables). Moreover, crop and primary crop self-sufficiency (S_C and S_{PC}) consist of annual and perennial plants, and primary biomass self-sufficiency (S_{BM}) even adds products from different land use classes (crop- and grassland). In line with the mass-balance principle of material flow accounting and the applied conceptual framework of social metabolism (see Section 2.1), we account for all self-sufficiency indices in dry mass (see also Krausmann et al., 2008).

Table 1
Abbreviations and explanations of variables and indices.

Variables/indices	Abbr.	Explanation
Production variables (incl. losses until farm gate)		
Ruminant livestock products	P _R	Milk and meat from cattle, sheep and goats
Monogastric livestock products	P _M	Eggs, pork, poultry meat
Cropland products	P _C	Harvested crops
Grassland products	P _G	Harvested grass
Consumption variables (incl. losses from farm gate to retail and waste)		
Human consumption of ruminant livestock products	C _R	Milk and meat from cattle, sheep and goats
Human consumption of monogastric livestock products	C _M	Eggs, pork, poultry meat
Human crop consumption	C _{C,pop}	Crops used for food and other uses (incl. seed and losses)
Livestock feed from cropland	C _{C,lst}	Crops used for feed
Crops embodied in livestock products consumption	C _{C,emb}	Feed crops required for production of consumed livestock products
Grass embodied in livestock products consumption	C _{G,emb}	Grass required for production of consumed livestock products
Self-sufficiency indices		
Ruminant products self-sufficiency	S _R	Relates ruminant milk and meat production and consumption
Monogastric products self-sufficiency	S _M	Relates eggs, pork and poultry meat production and consumption
Livestock products self-sufficiency	S _L	Relates ruminant milk and meat, eggs, pork and poultry meat production and consumption
Crop self-sufficiency	S _C	Relates harvested crops with crops used for food, other uses and feed
Primary crop self-sufficiency	S _{PC}	Relates harvested crops with crops used for food, other uses and feed crops required to produce consumed livestock products
Primary grass self-sufficiency	S _{PG}	Relates harvested grass with grass required to produce consumed ruminant products
Primary biomass self-sufficiency	S _{BM}	Relates harvested crops and grass with crops used for food, other uses and crops and grass required to produce consumed livestock products

2.3. Typology of regions according to their self-sufficiency profile

Assessing all dimensions of self-sufficiency for each region allows to classify them according to their self-sufficiency profiles. Fig. 3 provides an overview of the types we discern in this study. First, we distinguish regions according to crop (S_C) and primary crop self-sufficiency (S_{PC}). Regions in group A differ with regard to these two dimensions of SSR and are not further distinguished according to their livestock SSR. Regions in group B are not self-sufficient (i.e., net-import-dependent), and those in group C are self-sufficient (balanced or net-exporting) with regard to both indices. Regions in sub-groups 1 are net-importers of both, ruminant (R) and monogastric (M) livestock products. Regions in sub-groups 2 are either self-sufficient in terms of one type of livestock product. Regions in sub-groups 3 are self-sufficient in both types of livestock products. We did not include the primary grass self-sufficiency (S_{PG}) in the typology due to high uncertainties in grazing assessments (including those by CAPRI - see Section 4.3.). Additionally, the typology aims to understand the patterns of EU regions regarding their (dis-) connectedness of land-use, livestock production, and human consumption and trade of grass harvest over long distances is somewhat restricted.

2.4. Data

Data has been compiled from various sources, with a special emphasis on sub-national scale livestock systems. On the production

side, the Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact (CAPRI) model served as the primary data source (Data source: CAPREG - 21.03.2018 - see Britz and Witzke, 2014; Kempen and Witzke, 2018). Wherever possible, the CAPRI dataset relies on Eurostat statistics and is further supplemented by national and other well-documented data and includes a valid consolidation routine for missing values. CAPRI is a commonly used tool to analyze policies within the European Union (Leip et al., 2008). In our analysis, agricultural production comprised primary production on cropland and grassland, livestock production, and feed consumption. Moreover, we complemented the dataset with information on land area and livestock units (Eurostat, 2021a, 2021b) to calculate livestock densities. Table S1 in Supplementary Information (SI) provides an overview of all data sources.

To estimate feed demand, we developed region-specific feed conversion ratios (FCRs) based on data from the CAPRI model. We understand FCRs as the feed consumption required to produce one unit of a specific output, e.g., milk. For that, feed consumption of 16 animal activities (e.g., dairy cows production activity low yield, heifers raising activity) was allocated to five animal products (i.e., milk, beef, pork, eggs, poultry). While this is straightforward for products from pigs, laying hens, and broilers, the milk and beef system is highly interlinked and falls short to reduce feed intake for milk to those for dairy cows. Based on the cattle chain in the herd flow model in CAPRI (Britz and Witzke, 2014), we allocated a share of feed for breeding heifers and raising female calves from beef to milk in each region. A representation of the herd model and allocation can be found in Section 3 in the SI. The total feed for each product was then divided by the total product output to obtain average product-specific FCRs (see also Fig. S2 in SI). Due to the minor importance of products from sheep and goats and an incomplete data set among the regions, we aggregated those with the milk and meat from bovines, denoted as ruminant products.

On the consumption side, FAOSTAT Commodity Balances available at the national level were the data sources for human crop and animal product consumption (FAOSTAT, 2021a, 2021b). Human consumption comprises food and non-food use, including seed and supply chain losses (from farm gate to retail), as reported by FAOSTAT. Equally, data reported by FAOSTAT Commodity Balances includes waste resulting from retailing, food service, and household activities and, thus, are accounted for in human consumption. To derive consumption quantities on a sub-national level, we downscaled per capita human consumption with population numbers in each region.

All quantitative data were converted into dry mass by applying standard factors from Krausmann et al. (2008). The geographical resolution is mainly based on level 2 of the geocode standard by the European Union named Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS2), which subdivides EU countries into sub-national organizational units. In accordance with the CAPRI dataset and the reference year 2012, we referred to the NUTS2 definition from 2010. For six metropolitan regions (Vienna, Brussels, Berlin, Bremen, Hamburg, and London), no production data is reported by CAPRI as agricultural production only plays a minor role in urban areas. For these regions, we assumed average national cropland yields on area reported by Eurostat (2021a), no livestock production, and average national FCR to calculate primary biomass self-sufficiencies. In total, 226 NUTS regions in 25 countries (NUTS0) were analyzed. In some cases, the regional unit level is NUTS1 (United Kingdom), or even NUTS0 (e.g., Denmark), if reported accordingly by CAPRI. The focus of the study is the European Union, but we also included regions from the United Kingdom (despite their withdrawal from the European Union in the year 2020), and excluded Croatia, Malta and Cyprus due to a lack of data (also see Section 2 in SI for more specifications). The average area of all regions amounted to 19,047 km² (min: 162 km²; max: 165152 km²) and the average population was 2.2 Mio inhabitants (min: 0.03 Mio. max: 11.9 Mio.).

Self-sufficiency dimension	Production	Consumption	Formula
Livestock products		$S_R = P_R / C_R$ $S_M = P_M / C_M$ $S_L = (P_R + P_M) / (C_R + C_M)$	
Crop		$S_C = P_C / (C_{c, pop} + C_{c, lst})$	
Primary biomass		$S_{PC} = P_{C^*} / (C_{c, pop} + C_{c, emb})$ $S_{PG} = P_G / C_{G, emb}$ $S_{BM} = (P_{C^*} + P_G) / (C_{c, pop} + C_{c, emb} + C_{G, emb})$	

Fig. 2. Definition of self-sufficiency dimensions. Primary biomass dimension depicts the 'biomass footprint' of human food consumption and encompasses hypothetical feed crops and grass flows assuming a 100 % domestic production. P_{C^*} equals P_C plus used straw. S_L , S_{PG} and S_{BM} are in grey because they are not considered in the typology. Grass is assumed not to be traded (see text). The green arrow indicates the application of feed conversion ratios (FCR). Variables are explained in detail in Table 1.

3. Results

3.1. Livestock products self-sufficiency

Both livestock-product related SSRs, i.e. for ruminant products (milk and meat; S_R) and products from monogastric animals (pork, poultry, eggs; S_M) showed a wide range, from zero up to 10 (Fig. 4). The average ratio for ruminant products was 1.4 (median: 1.1) and for products from monogastric animals 1.2 (median: 0.8) over the entire European Union.

For ruminant products, 54 % (121 out of 226) regions served as net-supplying regions, representing 44 % of the total EU population and 59 % of the total EU area. For example, mountainous regions with a low percentage of cropland and a high share of grassland area (e.g., Tyrol in Austria, the Aosta Valley in Italy or Cantabria in Spain) were net-exporters of ruminant products. Mainly, these regions belonged to crop-importing regions ($S_C < 1$; see Section 3.2). Accordingly, 46 % of the regions were dependent on imports, with a population share of 56 % and an area share of 41 % (Fig. 4a).

For monogastric products, 39 % (88 regions) of the regions served as net-suppliers to other regions, and 61 % (138) of the regions relied on net-supply from outside their boundaries (Fig. 4b). The share of self-sufficient regions with products from monogastric animals was close to the share of total EU population living in these regions (36 %) and the percentage of total EU area they account for (40 %). In contrast, 54 % of ruminant-self-sufficient regions represented only 44 % of the total EU population. This indicates that ruminant production in the European Union was located in less populated and larger regions than production from monogastric animals. Moreover, fewer regions within the European Union were self-sufficient in monogastric products than with ruminant products (88 vs. 121 regions). The relation between ruminant and monogastric self-sufficiency was particularly nuanced in mountainous regions such as in the North of Spain and South-West of Austria.

Not only urban areas were dependent on the supply of both products from ruminants and monogastric animals. Also, southern regions across

the Mediterranean Sea (e.g., Tuscany and Calabria in Italy, Languedoc-Roussillon and Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur in France and Andalusia and Valencia in Spain) produced fewer livestock products than their population consume. Only 28 % (64 regions) produced sufficient livestock products to supply the domestic population with both livestock types.

3.2. Crop and primary biomass self-sufficiency

Fig. 5a presents the SSR for cropland products (S_C) for sub-national EU regions. The harvest of cropland products exceeded the domestic demand up to fivefold in certain regions, whereas others approached zero self-sufficiency. 41 % (92 out of 226 regions) had SSRs above 1 (marked in blue), thus served as net-exporters of cropland products. These regions harbored 33 % of the total EU population and 43 % of the total land area. Regions with cropland production exceeding domestic demand by humans and livestock were widely distributed among almost all countries of the European Union (only 5 countries did not include at least one net-exporting region). In particular, three regions in the hinterland of Paris (France) were the top net-exporting regions (Champagne-Ardenne, Picardy, Centre). Accordingly, 59 % (134 out of 226 regions) had SSRs below 1, indicating them as net-importers. The latter predominantly applied to metropolitan areas such as Brussels, London or Berlin, but not only. Moreover, almost all regions along the Alpine range as well as at the Mediterranean coast were net-importers of cropland products, among others.

The average primary biomass consumption comprising feed from crop- and grassland required to produce livestock products ($C_{c, emb}$ and $C_{g, emb}$), direct food, and other uses ($C_{c, pop}$) amounted to 1.26 t dm/yr per capita (Fig. 5b). The direct average per capita product consumption, which accounts for livestock products (C_R and C_M), direct food, and other uses ($C_{c, pop}$) was 0.42 t dm/yr. Thus, on average, 1 t of consumed products was associated with 3.0 t of primary biomass. The larger range among regions of primary biomass consumption compared to product consumption (Fig. 5b) resulted of different data resolution (i.e., region-specific feed conversion efficiencies for calculating primary biomass

Fig. 3. Decision tree indicates criteria for categorizing EU regions (=typology) according to self-sufficiency profiles.

and national resolution for product consumption). This reflects a higher differentiation of livestock production systems than human consumption patterns among sub-national regions in the European Union.

Comparing the primary crop consumption to the respective domestic crop harvest ('primary crop self-sufficiency' – S_{PC}), 45 % (101 out of 226) of EU regions domestically produced more than consumed directly as food and virtually through the consumption of livestock products (Fig. 5c). In other words, 45 % of EU regions produced sufficient primary cropland products for their hypothetical feed demand, direct food, and other uses, assuming that all livestock products were of domestic origin.

These regions harbored 35 % of the total EU population and covered 48 % of the EU area.

Patterns of crop (S_C) and primary crop (S_{PC}) self-sufficiency were similar but differed in 41 regions (18 %) concerning 19 % of the total EU population and 20 % of the total land area. Fig. 5d shows the correlation between the ratios of these two self-sufficiency dimensions (Fig. 6a maps these regions). 25 regions net-imported crops ($S_C < 1$), although domestic production was sufficient for the supply of the population with food and feed required for the consumption of livestock products ($S_{PC} \geq 1$ – violet box in Fig. 5d). In contrast, 16

Fig. 4. Livestock SSRs: a) ruminant livestock products (milk and meat; S_R) [left] and b) monogastric livestock products (pork, eggs, poultry; S_M) [right]. Regions with values below 1 (colored in red) are net-importing, and regions with values equal or greater 1 (in blue) are balanced or net-exporting.

Fig. 5. Panel shows a) a map of crop self-sufficiency (S_C); b) boxplots presenting the distribution of per capita product and primary biomass consumption among EU regions ($n = 226$); c) a map of primary crop self-sufficiency (S_{PC}); d) the correlation of crop (S_C) and primary crop self-sufficiency (S_{PC}), where the size of the bubbles indicate livestock self-sufficiency (S_L) and the green and violet boxes highlight those regions, which differ in terms of S_C and S_{PC} ; e) a map of primary grass self-sufficiency (S_{PG}) and f) a map of primary biomass self-sufficiency (S_{BM}). In the maps, regions with values below 1 (colored in red) are not self-sufficient and regions with values greater or equal 1 (in blue) are self-sufficient.

regions were net-exporter of crops ($S_C \geq 1$), but domestic production was insufficient to satisfy the population's primary biomass requirements ($S_{PC} < 1$ – green box in Fig. 5d). Interestingly, all regions in the first group were self-sufficient in terms of livestock products (avg. $S_L = 3.2$), while regions in the second group were not self-sufficient (avg. $S_L = 0.6$).

Harvested grass restricted the domestic primary biomass demand in fewer regions compared to crop harvest. Thus, more regions are primary grass self-sufficient (S_{PC}) than primary crop self-sufficient (S_{PC}). In 66 % of EU regions (150 out of 226) the domestic harvest on grasslands

amounted to or exceeded the gross demand embodied in consumed ruminant products (S_{PC} ; see Fig. 5e). These regions were inhabited by 54 % of the population and occupy 71 % of EU area.

Overall, the agricultural harvest on cropland and grassland sufficed in 57 % of EU regions (128 out of 226, 47 % of population and 64 % of area) to fulfill the primary biomass demand of the local population, whereas 53 % of the population relied on biomass production beyond the region's boundaries (Fig. 5f). A map illustrating the primary biomass deficit resp. surplus on a per capita basis is provided in the SI.

Fig. 6. Maps show the three main sub-groups of the categorization according to self-sufficiency profiles. a) group A comprises of regions diverging in direct and primary crop self-sufficiencies (S_C and S_{PC}), b) group B comprises of regions dependent on crop imports, and c) group C comprises of crop-exporting regions. Map legends: Red indicate SSRs < 1 , and blue indicate SSRs > 1 . d) Map shows the typology and is an overlap of groups A, B and C.

3.3. Self-sufficiency profiles

Based on the direct and primary crop self-sufficiency (S_C and S_{PC}), we differentiated between 3 main groups of regions. Group A consists of regions that differ in crop and primary crop self-sufficiency (all regions highlighted in both the violet and green box in Fig. 5d), while regions in B and C overlap in these self-sufficiencies but are distinguished based on livestock products self-sufficiency. The pattern of EU regions according to their self-sufficiency profiles is displayed in Fig. 6 and described in Table 2.

Group A regions show a diverging sign of crop and primary crop self-sufficiency (Fig. 5d and Fig. 6a). Regions in group A1 (violet) are characterized by net-importing crop products to produce livestock products for export indicated by a mean livestock self-sufficiency (S_L) of 3.2. While these regions harbored 10 % of the EU population and covered 13 % of the total EU area, they kept 30 % of the EU's total livestock (in LSU – see Table 2). In theory, the harvested biomass from cropland sufficed to meet human crop demand and the demand required for consumed livestock products (i.e., domestic feed for livestock production was available). Conversely, regions in Group A2 (5d, green box) net-exported cropland products and net-imported livestock products due to small livestock herds. Under current consumption patterns, cropland production did not provide sufficient biomass harvest for domestic demand.

Group B regions (Fig. b) were net-importers of crops, measured as both direct and primary self-sufficiency. In these regions, cropland shares of total regional area were below-average (14–30 %), except for regions in subgroup B2M (ruminant net-importers and net-exporters of products from monogastric animals). Group B1 regions, which were dependent on net-imports on all dimensions (i.e., direct, primary crops, and livestock products), made up 26 % of all regions and 21 % of total EU area, but 35 % of total EU population. Group B1 regions not only encompass urban areas, but in general regions

with low relevance of agriculture (due to forest-dominated land cover or marginal lands). Regions in group B2R were net-exporting ruminant livestock products, while net-importing crops and monogastric livestock products. Regions in Group B3 (6% of regions) covered 4 % of the EU area but inhabited 10 % of total livestock in the EU. We found the highest mean livestock density (138 LSU/km²) in regions of group B3. They exported both sorts of livestock products, albeit depending on crop imports.

Group C regions (Fig. 6c) were self-sufficient from crop and primary crop perspective. They were net-exporters of crops and produced sufficient crops required for domestic production of livestock products. Group C encompassed 34 % of all regions but 24 % of the EU population. These regions often surrounded urban agglomerations such as Madrid, Paris, Berlin, or Vienna. Group C1 comprise of 9 regions with average livestock SSRs of 0.6 for both sorts of livestock products, indicating net-imports of livestock products, despite the potential availability of sufficient crop biomass for the production of domestic demand levels. However, only 22 % of regions in this group harvested the amounts of grass sufficient for domestic production. Regions in group C2R (10 % of all regions) were only net-import-dependent with monogastric livestock products despite the availability of feed requirements for these products. In contrast, regions in group C2M were only import-dependent in terms of ruminant livestock products, despite the availability of feed crops. However, only 67 % of the regions within this group also harvested sufficient grass to meet the demand embodied in consumption of ruminant products. Group C3 (14% of regions) summarized full providing regions with SSRs above 1 in all dimensions (including primary grass self-sufficiency).

4. Discussion

We here provide a comprehensive analysis of the relation between agricultural production and consumption in 226 regions in

Table 2

Characteristics of categories: size of groups, arithmetic mean (\bar{x}) of self-sufficiency variants within group, arithmetic mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD) of selected parameters.

Group		Crop self-sufficient net-importers	Crop import-dependent net-exporters	Full net-importers	Crops and monogastric net-importers	Crops and ruminant net-importers	Crops-only net-importers	Crops-only net-exporters	Crops and ruminant net-exporters	Crops and monogastric net-exporters	Full net-exporters
Sub-group		A	A	B	B	B	B	C	C	C	C
		1	2	1	2R	2M	3	1	2R	2M	3
Share of EU total regions	N	25	16	59	28	9	13	9	23	12	32
Ruminant products self-sufficiency	%	11%	7%	26%	12%	4%	6%	4%	10%	5%	14%
Monogastric products self-sufficiency	\bar{x}	3.0	0.6	0.4	2.0	0.7	2.8	0.6	1.8	0.7	1.9
Crop self-sufficiency	\bar{x}	3.2	0.5	0.2	0.5	2.1	2.8	0.6	0.7	1.3	1.7
Primary crop self-sufficiency	\bar{x}	0.7	1.2	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.4	2.2	1.8	1.5	1.7
Primary grass self-sufficiency	\bar{x}	1.6	0.8	0.3	0.6	0.6	0.6	1.6	1.9	1.4	2.5
Total biomass self-sufficiency	\bar{x}	4.8	1.3	1.0	3.0	1.0	2.9	1.0	2.9	2.6	2.9
Share of primary grass self-sufficient regions in group	%	2.2	0.8	0.4	1.1	0.7	1.2	1.4	2.1	1.4	2.5
Area [km ²]	\bar{x}	100%	31%	20%	100%	33%	92%	22%	100%	67%	100%
	SD	21 747	20 754	15 204	25 255	17 297	11 824	12 674	19 803	21 857	21 362
Share of EU total area	%	12 802	23 565	24 574	31 336	9 229	13 028	12 121	17 259	12 293	20 442
Cropland in % of total area	\bar{x}	13%	8%	21%	16%	4%	4%	3%	11%	6%	16%
	SD	37%	33%	22%	14%	30%	20%	41%	35%	41%	44%
Livestock units [mio LSU]	\bar{x}	16%	16%	14%	13%	12%	13%	7%	14%	13%	12%
	SD	1.6	0.4	0.2	0.6	0.9	1.0	0.2	0.5	0.5	0.6
Share of EU total LSU	%	1.3	0.4	0.2	0.6	0.8	0.7	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.4
Livestock density [LSU/km ²]	\bar{x}	30%	4%	9%	12%	7%	10%	1%	8%	5%	14%
	SD	88	19	19	38	77	138	16	29	24	34
Population [mio cap]	\bar{x}	58	7	17	35	88	122	10	16	9	22
	SD	2.0	2.7	2.9	1.9	3.2	2.2	1.2	1.7	2.1	1.4
Share of EU total population	%	1.4	2.2	2.3	1.9	2.3	2.1	1.0	1.1	1.2	0.7
Population density [cap/km ²]	\bar{x}	10%	9%	35%	11%	6%	6%	2%	8%	5%	9%
	SD	129	168	754	145	215	279	129	109	109	96
	SD	89	85	1 311	175	140	192	98	72	66	55

the European Union. Since livestock systems have an intermediate role within food supply chains (i.e., as producers of animal-sourced products and consumers of primary biomass), these two perspectives need to be integrated when assessing self-sufficiency ratios (SSR). For that, we applied the consumption-based approach from footprint accounting (explained in Section 2.2) in order to develop a set of self-sufficiency ratios which relate agricultural biomass production with direct, respectively primary biomass demand. As a result, the self-sufficiency profiles provide a multi-dimensional perspective on regional food self-sufficiency and allow for implications for sustainability measures.

4.1. Insights from self-sufficiency profiles for short food supply chains

We showed that 14 % of EU regions, covering 16 % of the total EU area and harboring 9 % of the total EU population (Group C3; full net-exporters), produce sufficient livestock products and harvest sufficient crops, feed crops and grass to meet their local demand (current production and consumption patterns). These regions stand in stark contrast to 26 % of regions (21 % of the total EU area, 35 % of the total EU population), for which we found import-dependency on all analyzed dimensions (B1; full-net importers). Our results reveal the deep embeddedness of regions within a web of exchange with agricultural products on several stages of the supply chain, ensuring food security in the European Union. This corroborates with findings from a recent global study indicating that only 11–28 % of the global population can be supplied by agricultural production within a 100 km-radius (Kinnunen et al., 2020). Further, our results suggest that the reliance of regions on their close and distant hinterland does not only apply to urban areas with high population densities, for which this has been presented repeatedly (Goldstein et al., 2017; Kaufmann et al., 2021; Lauk et al., 2022; Vicente-Vicente et al., 2021). Also, mountainous regions specialized in ruminant production, boreal regions with low cropland availability, and regions with high livestock densities are highly dependent on net-imports to ensure food supply. Full net-importers, hence, show a great heterogeneity in regard to their livestock production systems (see Table S3 in SI-Section 7) (Dumont et al., 2018; Hercule et al., 2017).

Local food systems are favorable due to reduced emissions from transport requirements (Pradhan et al., 2020) and healthier diets by the availability of fresh food (Sonnino, 2013). We found a potential possibility for domestic supply for regions in group A1 and C. Further, many B1-urban areas were surrounded by group C-regions (net-exporters) which constitutes options for local or regional food systems. However, our findings also indicate limitations in providing sufficient biomass to feed domestic people and livestock locally. Trade ensures sufficient food supply in the European Union, particularly on the sub-national scale. Interestingly, it is argued that trade both mitigates and increases the systemic threat to food security, e.g., through global food price shocks (de Raymond et al., 2021). Moreover, closed borders and nationalist tendencies during the COVID-19 pandemic starting in 2020 have demonstrated the possible impacts of the ceased food supply by trading partners (Bisoffi et al., 2021). Together with the high import-dependency of EU regions shown in this study, the latter underlines the necessity of diversifying activities at the field, farm, market, and household level to enhance food system resilience (de Raymond et al., 2021; Hertel et al., 2021). This would allow to profit from the advantages of short food supply chains and simultaneously ensure food security. Also, in regard to political self-sufficiency strategies, it might be helpful to specifically consider the socio-ecological context and understand food self-sufficiency rather as a continuum of domestic and imported food supply than fostering domestic production by all means (Clapp, 2017).

4.2. Insights from self-sufficiency profiles for integrated crop-livestock systems

The multi-dimensional analysis of self-sufficiencies revealed that one-fifth of all EU regions are net-importers of crops while they were self-sufficient or even net-exporting livestock products (Groups A1, B2M, and B3). These regions cover a similar share of the total EU area as well as of the total EU population but almost half of all livestock of the European Union. This corresponds to observations by INRA (2016) that one-third of livestock in the European Union is concentrated within a small number of regions in Denmark, the Netherlands, northern Germany, and western France, particularly dairy, pigs, and poultry. Consequently, domestic livestock feed demand exceeded the net primary production potential in one-third of the EU's livestock systems (Mayer et al., 2021a). Hence, only feed imports enable livestock production at this scale.

The concurrence of crop imports and exports of livestock products underlines the observation of a 'footloose' industrial and specialized livestock sector (Naylor et al., 2005). The term 'footloose' denotes a livestock system that is disconnected from local land in terms of feed supply and manure output and utilization, i.e., fertilization. For example, Billen et al. (2012) showed historically how specialization spatially separated cereal production in the Seine watershed and animal farming in the North and West of France. Le Noë et al. (2017) further showed the high environmental losses of specialized systems and trade-induced open nutrient cycles within the same regions. Both studies corroborate our typology, classifying the regions Lower Normandy, Pays de la Loire, and Brittany as crop-importing and livestock products exporting regions (Group A1). However, regions in group A1 (crop self-sufficient net-importers) encompass a broader diversity of livestock systems than groups B2M (crops and ruminant net-importers) and B3 (crops-only net-importers) – see Table S3 in SI. While the latter (B2M and B3) predominantly consists of regions with high livestock densities, the former (A1) range from regions with medium livestock systems with crop production, grassland-based livestock systems to fodder-based regions with high livestock densities (Dumont et al., 2018; Hercule et al., 2017).

To close nutrient cycles and reduce economic costs, it has been suggested to relocate livestock production within the European Union (van Grinsven et al., 2018). The self-sufficiency profiles presented here can serve as an entry point for identifying regions with crop potential for relocation of livestock. The regions in Group C1 are characterized by average crop self-sufficiency (S_C) of 2.2 and primary crop self-sufficiency (S_{PC}) of 1.6, while both livestock self-sufficiencies (S_R and S_M) are 0.6. Similarly, regions in groups C2M and C2R were crop and primary crop self-sufficient (S_C and $S_{PC} > 1$) and import ruminant resp. monogastric products (S_R or $S_M < 1$). These values suggest the potential availability of sufficient biomass to meet the demand of feed required for livestock products, food, and other uses, despite a current shortage of locally produced livestock products.

4.3. Uncertainty of livestock feed efficiency

Livestock systems use 70 % of global agricultural land (Zanten et al., 2018) and 58 % of total harvested biomass (Krausmann et al., 2008). Furthermore, feed conversion efficiencies differ among livestock systems (Herrero et al., 2013), globally, and throughout the European Union (Hou et al., 2016; Mayer et al., 2021a). Despite this importance for agricultural land use, data availability for biomass flows to and from livestock systems is extremely scarce, in particular on the regional level. Additionally, region-specific information on livestock feed is scarce, particularly for biomass that is hardly traded via agricultural markets, i.e. homegrown feed and grassland biomass. The absence of comprehensive census data on grazing and biomass harvest on grassland considerably increases the uncertainty in available assessments (Fetzel et al., 2017).

In this study, we estimate region-specific feed conversion rates (FCR) based on outputs of the CAPRI model, which has been established for and is widely used in assessments of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) of the European Union (see Section 2.4). Yet, data quality of CAPRI has been subject to discussion. For example, forage feed ratios were considered unfeasibly high in a study on the European livestock sector (Karlsson et al., 2021). In light of feed data resulting from an economic partial equilibrium model built to examine EU agricultural policy, observed high uncertainties are expectable as those are not the primary goal. However, CAPRI constitutes one of the most comprehensive data reservoirs in the EU agricultural sector, particularly on the sub-national level. To assess the uncertainty of our results related to the choice of data source for livestock feed, we additionally calculate primary biomass consumption and establish the described categorization with feed data from three alternative references. The methodology is described in more detail in the Supporting Information (SI).

According to our results based on CAPRI (see Figs. 5b and 7a), the average primary biomass consumption is 1.26 t of dry matter per capita (range: 0.80–2.42 t dm/cap; median: 1.21). The calculation of primary biomass consumption applying alternative data for feeding efficiencies, i.e., the ones published by Bouwman et al. (2005) and Herrero et al. (2013), reveal similar, but less widely distributed values (avg. 1.34 t dm/cap; range: 0.89–1.85 t dm/cap; median: 1.34 and avg. 1.27 t dm/cap; range: 0.88–1.84 t dm/cap; median: 1.30). The smaller ranges can be explained by the smaller number of regions with different feed data (2 resp. 5 regions) in comparison to CAPRI (226). The primary biomass consumption resulting from the application of feed conversion ratios for 25 European countries published by Hou et al. (2016) is slightly lower and amounts to 1.02 t of dry

matter per capita on average (range: 0.76–1.5 t dm/cap; median: 0.97) (see Fig. 7a).

Alternative levels of primary biomass consumption result in changes in primary crop and grass self-sufficiencies (S_{PC} , S_{PG}) of the regions (Fig. 7b). The number of primary crop self-sufficient regions decreased by 4 % applying FCRs by Bouwman et al. (2005) and increased by 8 % and 4 % applying factors by Herrero et al., 2013 and Hou et al. (2016), respectively, compared to the result with CAPRI factors. In contrast, while the numbers of primary grass self-sufficient regions change in a similar magnitude for efficiency calculations with Bouwman et al. (2005) and Hou et al. (2016), Herrero et al. (2013) result in a decrease of 19 %, indicating a higher variability in grazing data in the European Union.

However, according to all four references, 86 % of all regions (195 out of 226) remain classified within the same typology group also with alternative feed efficiency datasets. 8 % of regions ($n = 18$) change group in comparison to the typology based on CAPRI data according to one reference, but are classified in the same group according to the other two references. In 4 % of the regions ($n = 10$), the alternative references result in a different classification compared to CAPRI, and in 1 % of all regions ($n = 3$), all alternative FCR datasets result in a deviating group (see SI for a map depicting affected regions). Regarding the size of the groups, the most significant switch can be observed in group A1 (violet compartment in Fig. 7c). Calculation using feed data by Bouwman et al. (2005) reduces the number of regions in this group, while a calculation with Herrero et al. (2013) increases the value by 4 % in comparison to CAPRI. The typologies based on Herrero et al. (2013) and Hou et al. (2016) show similar patterns of switches, yet using Herrero et al. (2013) yielded the most changes of regions among the groups. These results show that the typology at hand is reproducible

Fig. 7. Uncertainty resulting from diverging feed data: a) distribution of primary biomass footprints according to four analyzed data references in 226 regions; b) bars indicate the share of regions switching from self-sufficient (>1) to not self-sufficient (<1) for primary crop (S_{PC} , light brown) and grass (S_{PG} , green) self-sufficiency; c) difference of group size in comparison to typology based on data from CAPRI model in % of total regions ($n = 226$).

to a great extent due to its high dependency on cropland products. Yet, only a handful of data assessments cover region-specific feed patterns despite their importance and diversity.

4.4. Implications for the understanding of agri-food systems

To summarize, three implications relate to the findings of our SSR calculations. First, a too-narrow focus on local food supply as a sustainability solution ignores the constraints of local food systems in the European Union. This concerns not only urban areas but also other regions with specific geo-natural circumstances such as mountainous or forest-dominated regions. The simultaneous interest in benefitting from local food production and in diverse and equal (short) trade relations can increase food system resilience, specifically in the face of global change (Bisoffi et al., 2021; Hertel et al., 2021; Sonnino, 2016).

Second, it becomes obvious that SSR of livestock products alone provides only one side of the coin. Without knowledge about the size of available input (i.e., feed availability), the significance of this indicator is restricted. Consuming almost 60 % of harvested biomass, the metabolic size of livestock systems must not be disregarded when domestic production and consumption of livestock products are related, and conclusions for domestic supply are drawn. As we have shown, 21 % of EU regions rely on imports to ensure self-sufficiency with livestock products (groups A1, B2M and B3 with $S_c < 1$ and $S_M > 1$).

Third, and closely connected to our second implication, our results underline the disconnectedness of land-use and livestock production, and of livestock production and human consumption as well (D'Odorico et al., 2014; Erb et al., 2009; Kastner et al., 2014). The specialization and industrialization process resulting in increased land-use efficiency through higher yields and lower feed conversion ratios is considered an essential pillar of global food security (Evenson and Gollin, 2003; Krausmann et al., 2013; MacDonald, 2013). Notwithstanding, in light of severe consequences on ecosystem services and the interruption of biogeochemical cycles, an emphasis on agroecological practices (e.g., a re-integration of crop and livestock systems) which avoid detrimental and profit from beneficial effects and secure global food supply is appropriate (Billen et al., 2021; Kalt et al., 2021; Mayer et al., 2021b; Jin et al., 2021). By identifying regions with excessive livestock systems and regions with cropland potential to produce domestic livestock feed, we contribute to an evidence-based discourse on relocating livestock and reducing the disconnectedness.

Due to the resource intensity of the livestock sector, reducing livestock heads further would free up agricultural area and, subsequently, increase local food self-sufficiency and decrease the disconnectedness between production and consumption. Decreasing the EU livestock sector is highly synergistic with related detrimental environmental impacts. For example, the livestock sector is currently responsible for 14.5 % of global greenhouse gas emissions (Gerber et al., 2013). Climate mitigation options often focus on reduced consumption of animal-sourced products in the Global North, ignoring chances of reducing livestock production while ensuring producers' income. For example, a combination of two innovative governance approaches - a market-based emissions trading system (cap-and-trade scheme) for animal products linked with a livestock-to-land ratio, which also addresses biogeochemical cycles - has been proven to address various environmental issues and functions across all sectors (Weishaupt et al., 2020). More concretely, the Netherlands' government decided on a plan in December 2021, which foresees a reduction of livestock numbers by one-third through financial compensation of relocations of animals, exiting the business, or an extensification of farming practices (Levitt, 2021).

Information on territorial patterns of production-consumption interrelations, such as the presented study, is the backbone of a better understanding of types of agri-food systems, particularly by including

a broader perspective on self-sufficiency. However, our study did not include specific sustainability assessments and, consequently, conclusions on the sustainability of particular practices or dynamics are out of the study's scope. Albeit, a combination of self-sufficiency types with impact assessments such as on the carbon cycle or biodiversity and/or including scenarios assuming, for example, altered production and consumption patterns promise useful next steps. Notwithstanding, the approach at hand is very much connected to sustainability issues and, hence, offers a guiding framework for researchers and policymakers in undertaking the sustainability transformation of agri-food systems.

Further, it must be noted that regions identified as self-sufficient in the presented study do not necessarily provide the specific products demanded by domestic livestock and the human population. Regional agricultural self-sufficiency indices require the aggregation of various products. In the prevailing study, we follow the mass-balanced principle of material flow accounting and assess self-sufficiency in dry matter. However, we do not match production and consumption for individual products. We consider the presented indices as proxies for the dry mass production and demand in a region, implying a direct crop substitution despite possible climatic and geographical restrictions. Matching regional production and demand in terms of energy or protein content also would result in a deviating self-sufficiency typology. Balancing protein production and demand increases the importance of protein feed (resulting in an even higher import-dependency of livestock-intensive regions). In contrast, energetic values (e.g., caloric) put more weight on fat-containing oil crops. Both result in deviating self-sufficiency indices in specific regions. However, we assume similar regional patterns and conclusions for typologies established on protein or energy self-sufficiency.

5. Conclusion

We here presented a multi-dimensional self-sufficiency analysis to inform about relations between agricultural production and consumption and encounter the complexity of biophysical flows within agri-food systems. Our analysis revealed a diverse picture of regional self-sufficiency in the European Union. Generally, the exchange between net-exporting and net-importing regions secures sufficient food supply among regions indicating trade to be a crucial hedge against food insecurity. In particular, not only urban areas, for which net-import-dependency is obvious but also many rural areas show this pattern, owing to their geo-natural circumstances or livestock densities. Livestock plays a crucial role for sustainable and circular resource use, particularly in regions where crop imports enable exports of livestock products disclosed by the multi-dimensional analysis of self-sufficiency. The resulting disconnectedness of land use and livestock production interrupts biogeochemical cycles within agro-ecosystems with severe consequences for the global climate and biodiversity within ecosystems. Our results provide a multi-dimensional assessment of the capacity of agri-food systems to supply the local demand for food and feed biomass and emphasize the necessity of policy makers to pay attention to the diverse implications for a sustainability transition among regions.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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